

give abundant $(M+Cl)^-$, M^- and $(M-Me)^-$ ions this technique was applied to these molecules. A few representative results from this analysis is given in Table 2. The results indicate that because of the simplicity, negative ion spectra of these compounds are ideal for finding their elemental compositions using moment analysis.

TABLE 2—ELEMENTAL COMPOSITION FROM MOMENT ANALYSIS

Compd. no.	Ion	Composition	Deviation of moment
2	$(M+Cl)^-$	$C_{12}H_8O_5Cl$	-0.0212
	M^-	$C_{12}H_8O_5$	0.0122
	$(M-Me)^-$	$C_{11}H_6O_5$	-0.0043
4	$(M+Cl)^-$	$C_{13}H_{10}O_5Cl$	-0.0191
	M^-	$C_{13}H_{10}O_5$	0.66
	$(M-Me)^-$	$C_{12}H_7O_5$	-0.0088
5	$(M+Cl)^-$	$C_{16}H_{18}O_5Cl$	-0.0302
	M^-	$C_{16}H_{18}O_5$	-0.0351
	$(M-Me)^-$	$C_{15}H_{16}O_5$	0.0117
6	$(M-Me)^-$	$C_{15}H_{16}O_5$	-0.0087
7	$(M+Cl)^-$	$C_{16}H_{20}O_5Cl$	-0.0005
8	M^-	$C_{15}H_{20}O_5$	0.0087

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Molecular Rearrangement. IV. Oxidation Products of Acetoxyaleuritic Acid Methyl Ester and Molecular Rearrangement of its Epoxide

JAYANTA BANERJEE^a, GITALI DUTTA^a, U. K. SOM^b,
K. E. HAQUE^c and C. P. DUTTA^{a*}

^aDepartment of Chemistry, University of Kalyani,
Kalyani-741 235

^bGovernment Quinine Factory, Mungpoo, Darjeeling
^cInstitute of Pharmacy, Kalyani-741 235

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IN continuation of our investigations¹ on the molecular rearrangement involving epoxide ring opening in pentacyclic triterpenoid skeleton, olean-14-en-28-carbomethoxy-3 β -yl acetate (1) was treated with *m*-chloroperbenzoic acid whence in addition to the desired epoxide olean-14 α ,15 α -oxido-28-carbomethoxy-3 β -yl-acetate (2), $C_{33}H_{52}O_5$, (M^+ , 528), m.p. 176–78°, two other interesting rearranged products, compounds (A) and (B) were isolated. The α -orientation of the epoxy function in 2 was justifiable from both pmr studies and mechanistic consideration. The mass spectra of 2 indicated the fragmentation pattern in agreement with that of olean type of triterpenoids².

Compound-A, $C_{33}H_{52}O_5$ (M^+ , 528), m.p. 190–92°, showed ir absorption bands at 3540 and 830 cm^{-1} attributable to a hydroxyl and a trisubstituted double bond. The carbonyl bands for ester and the acetate group appeared at 1740 and 1745 cm^{-1} as twin peaks. Pmr spectrum showed a overlapping multiplets in the region δ 0.8–1.16 which were assigned to seven tertiary-methyl groups and an ill-defined triplet at δ 5.36–5.44 (1H) due to olefinic proton at C_{12} . The low field shift of C_{18} -methine proton at δ 2.76 and 2.88 (1H, dd, J 4 Hz) was attributable due to allylic double bond at C_{12-13} and anisotropic effect of 28-carbomethoxy group. A one-proton double doublet at δ 4.02–4.20 (J ~11 and 5 Hz) after D_2O exchange suggested the presence of 15 β -axial proton in the molecule. The multiplicity of the downfield signal around δ 5.24–5.36 of the C_{15} -methine proton bearing the acetoxy function of the diacetate (4) also corroborated the presence of β -axial proton at C_{15} and thereby indicating the presence of a α -equatorial OH group at C_{15} . The formation of C_{15} - α -equatorial hydroxy group therefore confirmed the α -orientation of the epoxide since the configuration around C_{15} remains unaffected during opening of the epoxide ring. The mass spectral fragmentation pattern and the above spectral data identified the compound-A as olean-12-en-28-carbomethoxy-15 α -hydroxy-3 β -yl acetate (3). Besides the molecular ion peak at m/z 528, other significant fragmentations at m/z 249 and 219 (M^+ –250–59, 100%) were formed by retro-Diels-Alder cleavage of ring-C.

In conformity with the structure (3) compound-A upon acetylation with Ac_2O /pyridine furnished the

corresponding olean-12-en-28-carbomethoxy-3 β ,15 α -diacetate (4), m.p. 210–12°. The ir spectrum was devoid of hydroxyl absorption band at 3 540 cm⁻¹, present in the parent compound. The ¹H nmr spectrum of 4 which showed besides the usual singlet at δ 2.04 (3H) an additional singlet at δ 2.00 (3H) also confirmed the above observation. The C₁₅-methine proton bearing the acetoxy function was shifted downfield and it got merged with the C₁₂-olefinic proton around δ 5.36 (2H, m).

Mechanistically, the formation of the compound (3) from the epoxide (2) as intermediate may in probability be a stepwise process. The carbocation at C₁₄ first generated by the cleavage of the oxirane ring was subsequently stabilised by the migration of C₁₃-methyl group followed by elimination of C₁₂-H.

The minor product, compound-B, C₃₃H₅₀O₅ (M⁺, 526), m.p. 212–14°, was identified as 5. The compound showed in its ir spectrum a sharp band at 1 730 cm⁻¹ and 845 cm⁻¹ characteristic of carbonyl and trisubstituted double bond respectively. The ¹H nmr spectrum displayed an unresolved multiplet centered around δ 2.34 (2H) due to C₁₆-methylene protons α - to the C₁₅-keto group. The assignment of the keto group at C₁₅ and also the double bond at 12 : 13 position received confirmation from mass spectral fragmentation pattern, *m/z* 277, 248, 189 (100%). The ketone (5) is believed to be formed by oxidation of C₁₅-OH of compound-A (3) during the reaction. This assumption was verified by the formation of compound-B by the oxidation of compound-A with *m*-chloroperbenzoic acid in chloroform.

Action of BF₃-etherate on the epoxide (2) in dry benzene at room temperature yielded a product which was characterised as compound-A, previously obtained during the epoxidation reaction of 1 with *m*-chloroperbenzoic acid. Finally, the epoxide (2) on treatment with dry HCl gas in chloroform at room temperature furnished compound-A.

Formation of the 15 α -hydroxy compound (3) by the action of BF₃-etherate and dry HCl gas on epoxide (2) corroborated our belief that 3 is formed through the intermediacy of 2 according to the mechanism given in Chart 1.

Experimental

M.p.s. were determined using a Kofler hot-stage apparatus. Ir spectra were recorded with Perkin-Elmer 298 spectrophotometer and pmr spectra on a Jeol FX 100 MHz spectrometer, chemical shifts being reported as p.p.m. downfield tetramethylsilane. Compounds were purified by silica gel (60–120 mesh; Glaxo) column chromatography. The compounds were visualised as one spot on tlc of silica gel (Merck) layer. Anhydrous Na₂SO₄ was used for drying the solvent.

Epoxidation of olean 14-en-28-carbomethoxy-3 β -yl-acetate (1): A chloroform solution (75 ml) of

Chart 1

m-chloroperbenzoic acid (0.75 g) was added dropwise to a stirred solution of olean 14-en-28-carbomethoxy-3 β -yl-acetate (1; 0.75 g) in dry chloroform (75 ml) at 0–5° for 5 h. The completion of the reaction was monitored by tlc ethyl acetate-petroleum ether (b.p. 60°–80°), 1 : 9. The chloroform layer was washed with saturated sodium bicarbonate solution (3 × 50 ml) followed by water till neutral. It was dried, filtered and evaporated to furnish a white solid (0.70 g) showing three spots in the tlc. The solid was purified by column chromatography over silica gel (50 g).

Petroleum ether (b.p. 60–80°)-benzene (9 : 1) elution furnished olean-12-en-15-one-28-carbomethoxy-3 β -yl-acetate (compound-B, 5), m.p. 212–14°; ν_{\max} (KBr) 1 730 (acetoxy, six-membered ring ketone and carbomethoxy function), 1 270 (acetoxy) and 845 cm⁻¹ (olefinic double bond); δ_{H} (100 MHz; CDCl₃) 0.84–1.12 (21H, s, characteristic triterpenic methyl protons), 2.04 (3H, s, acetoxy), 2.28–2.4 (2H, m, *J* ~ 4.8 Hz methylene protons α - to the keto group), 3.56 (3H, s, carbomethoxy), 4.4–4.6 (1H, m, *J* ~ 6.5 Hz, α -proton at C₃) and 5.44–5.56 (1H, m, *J* ~ 4.0 Hz, olefinic proton at C₁₂); *m/z* 526 (M⁺, 5%), 511 (35), 496 (15), 451:(83), 436 (32), 277 (20), 262 (42), 248 (82), 203 (33) and 189 (100%).

Petroleum ether-benzene (4 : 1) elution yielded olean-14 α ,15 α -oxido-28-carbomethoxy-3 β -ylacetate (2), m.p. 176–78°; ν_{\max} (KBr) 1750 (acetoxy, carbomethoxy), 1270 (acetoxy) and 830 cm^{-1} (epoxide); δ_{H} (100 MHz; CDCl_3) 0.84–1.16 (21H, s, characteristic triterpenic methyl protons), 2.04 (3H, s, acetoxy), 3.20–3.28 (1H, d, $J \sim 6$ Hz, C_{15} -H), 3.68 (3H, s, carbomethoxy) and 4.40–4.56 (1H, m, $J \sim 6.5$ Hz, α -H at C_3); m/z 528 (M^+ , 93%), 510 ($M^+ - \text{H}_2\text{O}$, 20), 495 (5), 468 ($M^+ - 60$, 38), 408 ($M^+ - 60 - 60$, 12), 278 (52), 217 (45) and 189 (100%).

Further elution with benzene furnished olean-12-en-15 α -hydroxy-28-carbomethoxy-3 β -yl acetate (compound-A; 3), m.p. 190–92°; ν_{\max} (KBr) 3540 (hydroxy), 1745 and 1250 (acetoxy), 1740 (carbomethoxy) and 830 cm^{-1} (olefinic double bond); δ_{H} (100 MHz; CDCl_3) 0.80–1.16 (21H, s, characteristic triterpenic methyl protons), 2.04 (3H, s, acetoxy), 2.76 and 2.88 (1H, dd, $J \sim 4$ Hz, C_{18} -H), 3.64 (3H, s, carbomethoxy), 4.04–4.20 (1H, m, methine proton at C_{15} bearing hydroxyl), 4.44–4.6 (1H, m, $J \sim 7$ Hz, α -H at C_3) and 5.36–5.44 (1H, m, $J \sim 4$ Hz, olefinic proton at C_{12}); m/z 528 (M^+ , 57%), 510 ($M^+ - \text{H}_2\text{O}$, 22), 468 ($M^+ - 60$, 61), 450 (15), 408 ($M^+ - 60 - 60$, 17), 278 (91), 249 (7), 219 (100) and 189 (33%).

Acetylation of compound-A (3): Acetic anhydride (2 ml) was added to a stirred solution of olean-12-en-15 α -hydroxy-28-carbomethoxy-3 β -yl-acetate (3; 0.3 g) in dry pyridine (2 ml). The mixture was allowed to warm slowly for 6 h and poured over crushed ice. Usual work up followed by purification by column chromatography and crystallisation yielded olean-12-en-28-carbomethoxy-3 β -15 α -diacetate (4), m.p. 210–12°; ν_{\max} (KBr) 1720 (carbomethoxy), 1730, 1250 (acetoxy) and 830 cm^{-1} (olefinic double bond); δ_{H} (100 MHz; CDCl_3) 0.80–1.24 (characteristic triterpenic methyl protons), 2.0 and 2.04 (3H, s, two acetoxy groups), 2.76 and 2.88 (1H, dd, $J \sim 4$ Hz, C_{18} -H), 3.72 (3H, s, carbomethoxy), 4.44–4.6 (1H, m, $J \sim 6.5$ Hz, α -H at C_3) and 5.24–5.52 (2H, m, merged olefinic-H at C_{12} and C_{18} -H); m/z 570 (M^+ , 5), 510 ($M^+ - 60$, 59), 450 ($M^+ - 60 - 60$, 23), 390 ($M^+ - 60 - 60 - 60$, 15) and 189 (28).

BF_3 rearrangement of olean-14 α ,15 α -oxido-28-carbomethoxy-3 β -yl acetate (2): Olean-14 α ,15 α -oxido-28-carbomethoxy-3 β -yl-acetate (2; 0.2 g) was treated with BF_3 -etherate (0.2 ml) in dry benzene (20 ml) and the mixture was stirred for 30 min at room temperature. The reaction mixture was then neutralised with solid NaHCO_3 and washed with water till neutral. The organic layer was dried, filtered and evaporated to furnish a white solid (0.19 g) which upon chromatographic purification and subsequent crystallisation yielded a crystalline solid, m.p. 190–92°; it was found identical with olean-12-en-15 α -hydroxy-28-carbomethoxy-3 β -yl-acetate (3).

Dry HCl rearrangement of olean-14 α ,15 α -oxido-28-carbomethoxy-3 β -yl acetate (2): To a solution of olean-14 α ,15 α -oxido-28-carbomethoxy-3 β -yl acetate (0.2 g) in dry CHCl_3 (50 ml), dry HCl gas was passed

through for 3 h at room temperature. The CHCl_3 layer was then washed successively with NaHCO_3 and water and dried. The CHCl_3 layer was filtered and evaporated to furnish a white solid (0.18 g), which on chromatographic purification yielded a crystalline solid, m.p. 190–92°; it was found identical with olean-12-en-15 α -hydroxy-28-carbomethoxy-3 β -ylacetate (3).

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Synthesis of some Chalcones and their Antibacterial Activity

K. N. NAIK and H. B. NAIK*

Chemistry Department, South Gujarat University, Surat-395 007

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SEVERAL workers^{1,2} synthesised chalcones and related compounds using alkyl as well as halogen substituted *o*-hydroxyacetophenones. Alkyl group present in *o*-hydroxyacetophenone enhances its activities due to its electron-releasing nature and facilitates the formation of chalcones. It was thought interesting to study the effect of alkyl groups when present in *meta*- and *para*-positions of phenolic group in the synthesis of chalcones and related compounds. Chalcones have been reported to possess various biological activities³.

2-Hydroxy-4,5-dimethylacetophenone (1) was condensed with substituted-benzaldehydes in presence of potassium hydroxide (40%) and the reaction was complete in 18 h. The chalcones were obtained in good yields. This may be due to the presence of methyl group in *para*-position to ketonic group. Methyl group in *meta*-position to ketonic group may have no effect on reactivity of ketone as observed by Marathey¹.